

Altruism Behavior in Higher University: Role of Gratitude and Job Satisfaction

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Abstract

This study examines how *the role of volunteering (altruism)* that has an impact on job satisfaction felt by lecturers by paying attention to that in that voluntary role lecturers have a value of *gratitude* for their profession. This study will also analyze the mediating and moderating role of altruism behavior so that it has an impact on lecturer job satisfaction at several universities in Kupang City. This research is explanatory using saturated/census sampling techniques on 98 lecturer respondents at universities in Kupang City. The Analysis Tool uses Modmed Analysis (mediation moderation) with *Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)* equations with the help of SmartPLS Version 3.3. The results showed that: 1) gratitude had a positive and significant effect on lecturer job satisfaction; 2) gratitude has a positive and significant effect on altruism behavior; 3) altruism behavior has a positive and significant effect on lecturer job satisfaction, and 4) altruism behavior mediates the relationship between shaving and lecturer performance.

1. Introduction

Lecturers in carrying out their duties as professional lecturers related to the Tri Dharma of higher education, namely; carry out education and teaching; Research and community service as well as support are required to always improve their performance. This performance is measured from

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academic achievements fulfilled per semester which are reported through the Lecturer Performance Load (BKD) and Employee Performance Target (SKP).

In the two (2) documents, it is stated that lecturers will be faced with an increasingly heavy workload. The workload will certainly have an impact on decreasing the ability of apes. Therefore, of course, in his capacity, lecturers need to be aware of the relationship with their colleagues and these colleagues are able to provide help (empathy) which is done voluntarily. This voluntary role contains the context that there are empathetic values and a culture of mutual cooperation from colleagues that can provide help for colleagues when colleagues experience various difficulties in carrying out work, (Rani et al., 2019).

The value of empathy in the context of organizational behavior is referred to as organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) as expressed by ((Organ, 1988). This value is referred to as the role of altruism / voluntary role to help colleagues in the organization. This volunteer role certainly arises when every lecturer is able to realize the importance of his duties and roles as a teacher for students and of course for colleagues and the environment in which they work.

By realizing the importance of his profession as a lecturer, lecturers will certainly be grateful for the work they are currently doing. The realization of his duties and responsibilities is expressed as a form of gratitude. Gratitude is based on the situation of gratitude as an emotional and adaptive overflow from humans, namely the relationship between lecturers and the surrounding environment such as colleagues and leaders, (DEVI, 2019).

The phenomenon and initial observation in several universities in Kupang City, that often the role of volunteers to help fellow colleagues (lecturers) is still very low, for example in some cases to complete administrative work which is only focused on the ability of administrative employees; Lecturers who sometimes do not participate in campus activities are some interesting cases to be researched. Another case shows the face of gratitude that is not enjoyed by lecturers at several universities in Kupang City for their current profession regarding salaries, benefits, lecturer certification and other compensation which has an impact on the renhdanya of lecturer job satisfaction so that it has an impact on the declining performance of universities.

The important point and urgency of this study is the low altruism behavior of lecturers and the lack of gratitude of lecturers for every facility obtained and the lack of job satisfaction of lecturers. This study wants to examine and analyze gratitude, altruism behavior and job satisfaction of lecturers at several universities in Kupang City.

2. Theoretical review and Hypothesis Development

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

Organizational citizenship behavior is a choice or voluntary behavior that is not part of an employee's formal obligations, but effectively supports organizational functions, (Judge & Robbins, 2017) OCB is a behavior displayed by an employee voluntarily and beyond the required job role with a view to improving the effectiveness of organizational functions, even though such behavior is not included in the organization's reward system, (Organ, 1988) Furthermore, OCB is divided into five (5) indicators, including: 1) altruism; 2) politeness; 3) conscience; 4) citizen virtue, and 5) sportsmanship, (Organ, 1988).

Altruism (Voluntary Work Behavior)

Voluntary work behavior (altruism); behavior of assisting other members of the organization in their tasks, (Organ, 1988) for example: volunteering to help less skilled employees, helping new employees, helping colleagues who are overloaded with work or helping to work absent employees.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction refers to an individual's general attitude toward his or her job. A person with a high level of job satisfaction shows a positive attitude towards his job. Someone who is dissatisfied with his job shows a negative attitude towards work, (Judge & Robbins, 2017) Furthermore, job satisfaction is measured from 4 indicators, including: 1) the job itself; 2) appropriate rewards; 3) supportive working conditions, and 4) supportive co-workers, (Judge & Robbins, 2017).

Gratitude

Gratitude is a mood and mood that arises as an affectiousness f in a person that is related to individual attitudes and is accompanied by gratitude, (McCullough et al., 2002).

Behavioral Altruism and Job Satisfaction

Several previous studies examined the positive relationship between altruism behavior and job satisfaction, among others conducted by: (Indarti et al., 2017); (Lestari & Ghaby, 2018) and (Triyanto, 2009) Based on the study, the first hypothesis is:

H1: altruism behavior has a positive and significant effect on lecturer job satisfaction

Gratitude and Altruism Behavior

Some previous studies that examined the relationship between altruism and gratitude behavior include: ((Fauziyyah & Luzvinda, 2017); and (RIFKY, 2020)

H2: altruism behavior has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction

Gratitude and Job Satisfaction

Some previous studies examining the relationship between gratitude and job satisfaction include: (KARIM, 2021); (Pratama et al., 2015); (Suseno & Pramithasari, 2019) and (HISYAM et al., 2019). Based on the study, the third hypothesis is:

H3: Gratitude has a positive effect on lecturer job satisfaction

Altruism behavior as a mediator and moderation between gratitude and job satisfaction

Studies conducted by (RIFKY, 2020); (Rianto, 2023); (Simanjuntak, 2021); (Garg et al., 2019); and (Kim & Oh, 2020). Based on these studies, the fourth and fifth hypotheses are:

H4: behavioral altruism mediates the relationship between gratitude and job satisfaction Lecturer

H4: behavioral altruism strengthens the relationship between gratitude and job satisfaction Lecturer

Based on the theoretical studies and empirical studies described, our research model is presented as follows in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Model Research

3. Methodology

Nature and Types of Research

This research is quantitative research with an explanatory approach. (Field, 2013). Quantitative research states using numbers and statistical calculations with a view to testing hypotheses that have been built before. Furthermore, (Stebbins, 2001) states that basically explanatory research aims to investigate the causality relationship of two or more variables and find out the nature and pattern of the relationship between these variables.

Population and Research Sample

Population is a generalized area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characters set by researchers to draw conclusions, (Riyanto & Hatmawan, 2020). The population of this study is as many as 190 lecturers spread across the Faculty of Economics and majors in several universities both public and private universities in Kupang City with the following details:

1. Faculty of Economics and Business, Nusa Cendana University Kupang: 43 lecturers
2. Faculty of Economics and Business Widya Mandira Catholic University Kupang: 35 lecturers
3. Faculty of Economics, Artha Wacana Christian University Kupang: 28 lecturers
4. Faculty of Economics, University of Muhammadiyah Kupang: 23 lecturers
5. Department of Business Administration Kupang State Politkenik: 29 lecturers
6. KupangState Politkenik Accounting Committee: 25

Furthermore, for sampling used the 5% Slovin Formula, (Sugiyono, 2010) with the following details:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N (d)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{190}{1 + 190 (0,05)^2} = \frac{190}{1 + 0.457} = 125.55 = 126 \text{ lectures}$$

Based on these calculations, the number of samples in this study was 126 lecturers.

Instrument Measurement

The altruism behavior measurement model refers to (Organ, 1988) among others, in the form of: behavior helping certain people; changing colleagues; helping the work of overloaded colleagues; taking time for problems faced by colleagues; volunteering for office work. Gratitude refers to models (McCullough et al., 2002) among others: I feel grateful for what I have received in life; I feel grateful to something or someone; I sometimes feel grateful for the smallest things; and I thank everyone who helped. Job satisfaction adopts (Judge & Robbins, 2017) among others: 1) the job itself; 2) appropriate rewards; 3) supportive working conditions, and 4) supportive co-workers. All instruments are measured on a 5-point Likert scale ((Dawes, 2008) with a scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree).

Data Analysis

Data analysis is carried out in stages, the initial stage will be carried out in a statistical descriptive manner using the average value of each respondent's answer. Furthermore, the second stage was tested using path analysis which was processed using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) model with the SmartPLS version 3 program. 3. Partial Least Square (PLS) with several stages.

4. Results

Respondent Profile

The total population in this study is 126 lecturers spread across several universities in Kupang City, both public and private universities. The questionnaire return rate was 98 (78%) and the remaining 22% was not returned/damaged. So that respondents were obtained as many as 98 lecturers. The respondents' profiles are as follows: men as much as 55% and women 79%. Age of respondents: 30-40 years as much as 41%; 41-50 years as much as 48%; 51-60 years old as much as 29% and > 60 years as much as 16%. Education Level: Master 69% and Doctorate (31%) Working period: 0-5 years as much as 7%; 6-10 years as much as 49%; 11-15 years as much as 47%; 16-20 years old as much as 21% and 21 years old > as much as 11%.

Average Respondents' Answers

The average answers from each indicator include the following: Gratitude of 3.80 was obtained in the good category; Altruism behavior averaged 3.98 (good category) and job satisfaction was obtained on average of 3.89 (satisfied). The descriptive results show that the average answer is in the good category.

1. Instrument Testing

Instrument testing refers to the value of validity and reliability of each construct with reference to Cronbach's alpha value and composite reliability, ((Fornell & Larcker, 1981) which has a value of > 0.70, as stated by (Field, 2013). The model measurement results are presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Measurement Models

Variable	VIF	Loading	α	CR	AVE
Altruism Behavior			0.87	0.91	0.72
AB1		0.80			
AB2		0.90			
AB3		0.78			
AB4		0.90			
Gratitude			0.76	0.85	0.59
GR1		0.74			
GR2		0.87			
GR3		0.74			
GR4		0.70			
Job Satisfaction			0.83	0.88	0.65
JS1		0.81			
JS2		0.72			
JS3		0.85			
JS4		0.83			

Data Source: Primary Data, processed by author, August 2023

Direct Influence and Indirect Influence

The results of direct and indirect influence testing are presented in table 2 below.

Table 2. Direct Influence and Indirect Influence

Relationship of Variables	Path Coefficient	t-stat	P-Val.	Note
$GR \rightarrow JS$	0.231	2.831	0.005	Sig
$GR \rightarrow AB$	0.612	14.810	0.000	Sig
$AB \rightarrow JS$	0.326	5.728	0.000	Sig
$GR \rightarrow AB \rightarrow JS$	0.200	4.864	0.000	Sig

Data Source: Primary Data, processed by author, August 2023

The results of direct and indirect influence testing, (Baron & Kenny, 1986) are shown in the final model in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. Inner and Outer Model

5. Discussion

The Effect of Gratitude on Job Satisfaction

Gratitude has a direct positive and significant influence on lecturer job satisfaction (Table 2). The results showed that the more the lecturer was grateful for what was obtained, the higher the lecturer's job satisfaction. These results support previous studies conducted by: (Greguras & Diefendorff, 2010); (May et al., 2004). This study confirms that with the values of gratitude for what is achieved, being owned by lecturers eating will increase the lecturer's job satisfaction.

The Effect of Gratitude on Altruism Behavior

The test results show that gratitude has a direct positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. This study is in line with previous research conducted by: (Meynhardt et al., 2020); (Meynhardt, 2015) and (Watermeyer, 2012). Thus, the values of gratitude possessed by lecturers are improved, which will increase the altruism behavior of lecturers.

The Effect of Altruism Behavior on Job Satisfaction

Altruism behavior affects lecturer job satisfaction. The results of this study are different from studies conducted by: (Indarti et al., 2017); (Lestari & Ghaby, 2018) and (Triyanto, 2009).

The Mediating Effect of Altruism Behavior Between Gratitude and Job Satisfaction Relationships

Behavioral altruism mediates the relationship between gratitude and lecturer job satisfaction. The results of this study are in line with (RIFKY, 2020); (Rianto, 2023); (Simanjuntak, 2021); (Garg et al., 2019); and (Kim & Oh, 2020).

6. Conclusion

The conclusions that can be drawn are: 1) gratitude has a direct effect on lecturer job satisfaction and altruism behavior positively and significantly; 2) altruism behavior has a positive and significant effect on lecturer job satisfaction; and 3) behavioral altruism mediates the relationship between gratitude and lecturer job satisfaction. The results showed that both directly and indirectly altruism

behavior had a positive and significant effect on lecturer job satisfaction. Future studies need to examine in depth other factors that affect lecturer job satisfaction.

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